

EmpoWomen Open Call #1

Deliverable 2.1 Open Call Documentation

Prepared by: SPLORO

Description

Information package needed to publish each of the open calls including guidelines, online form, leaflets, and open call announcement for distribution.

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Disclaimer:

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Abstract:

The present document is the EmpoWomen "Open Call Documentation." This documentation outlines rules, procedures, and annexes that define the participation of startups in the acceleration program.

List of Acronyms

EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
ESR	Evaluation Summary Report
FSTP	Financial Support for Third Parties
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
VAT	Value Added Tax

Table of Contents

1.	The EmpoWomen Project.....	6
2.	Executive Summary	7
3.	Open Call Overview	7
4.	Attachments of the deliverable	9
5.	EmpoWomen Open Call #1	10
5.1	Introduction.....	10
5.2	Background	10
5.3	Open call objectives	11
5.4	Open Call #1 Documentation	11
5.5	Funding Scheme	12
5.6	Acceleration Programme Overview	13
5.7	Open Call Timeline	13
5.8	Additional information.....	13
	Annex 1. Guidelines for applicants.....	15
	Annex 2. Application Form.....	52
	Annex 3. Leaflet.....	66
	Annex 4. EmpoWomen Open call announcement.....	68

List of Figures

Figure 1.	Evaluation process.	8
Figure 2.	Timeline for submission, evaluation of proposals and acceleration programme for OC#1.	13

1. The EmpoWomen Project

The main goal of EmpoWomen is to create an exclusive support programme for female founders and entrepreneurs leading deep tech startups from widening-area countries to grow into tomorrow's female tech leaders and to put women at the forefront of deep tech in Europe.

The primary objective of the EmpoWomen program is to boost the development of startups led by women in the digital and advanced technology sectors. This program is conceived as a strategic tool to foster female leadership in technological innovation, positioning women as essential players in the field of advanced technologies in Europe.

EmpoWomen aims to allocate 1.5 million EUR to achieve its objectives, attracting more than 150 applications with the aim of selecting 25 deserving startups.

These financial resources will be distributed across three components for the startups. Firstly, each beneficiary startup can receive up to 45,000 EUR in equity-free cash. Additionally, beneficiaries will be provided with a comprehensive acceleration program, including access to specialized mentoring, tailored training for the specific needs of startups, and participation in exclusive events. Vouchers facilitating access to key services such as acceleration, mentoring, and training, provided by external entities not affiliated with the beneficiary consortium, will be granted. Each startup can receive up to 12,400 EUR in vouchers. Finally, upon the conclusion of the acceleration program, a showcase event, the Demo Day, will be held where all startups will present their achievements. In this event, three prizes will be awarded to the top three startups, with a value of 15,000 EUR for the first place, 11,500 EUR for the second, and 6,000 EUR for the third. This ensures compliance with the conditions set forth in the call, stipulating that no startup can receive more than 60,000 EUR in FSTP funding.

The startups will be selected through two open calls to be launched in January 2024 and December 2024. Eligible beneficiaries will be startups led by women in deep tech, legally established in the Widening Area.

During the next 2 years (November 2023 - October 2025), the EmpoWomen consortium, comprised of 4 partners with 8 startup associations from the widening area, will join forces to make this a reality.

2. Executive Summary

This document is deliverable 2.1 “Open Call documentation v1”. The present deliverable is primarily related to the first open call: EmpoWomen Open Call#1 (hereinafter “OC#1”). It compiles the documentation (which is defined as annexes of this document) that formalises the rules and procedures for startups’ (third parties) participation in the open call and respective funding programme.

This deliverable is developed within the framework of WP2. The objective of this WP (Women-led deep tech startups discovery), is to discover, attract and select high-quality female applicants to present solutions addressing the areas covered by the EmpoWomen programme.

This call provides up to 45,000 EUR per beneficiary to boost the growth and development of startups. Additionally, it offers an acceleration program that provides strong support, including business guidance, personalized assistance, access to an extensive network of key stakeholders, expert insights, and marketing opportunities.

The call aims to provide support to foster the development and investment potential of these startups, with the ultimate aspiration of turning them into prominent female figures in advanced technology innovation in Europe.

3. Open Call Overview

The EmpoWomen Open Call #1 runs from January 8, 2024, to March 8, 2024 (17:00 CET), coinciding with **International Women's Day**. All proposals must be submitted on the SPLORO platform (https://bit.ly/EmpoWomen_OC1)¹, which will be the entry point for submission and participation in the open call.

EmpoWomen OC#1 will provide funding to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and startups. The EmpoWomen open call will finance women-led startups in digital and deep tech that are legally established in the countries of the European Union widening area at the time of application. These startups should demonstrate strong growth and scalability potential, as well as a commitment to promoting gender equality in the technology industry. The equity-free funding is designed to assist these startups in overcoming initial financial barriers and advancing on their path to success.

The proposals will be evaluated against three criteria (using a score of 0 (Proposal fails to address the criterion) to 5 (excellent)):

Excellence: The Excellence criteria assess the alignment of the applicant's proposal with the specific requirements outlined in the call and the broader framework of the European Innovation Council (EIC). Additionally, the evaluation considers the degree of innovation, emphasizing deep-tech solutions that surpass current standards, assessing the likelihood of success, and evaluating the project's overall feasibility. The evaluators will also scrutinize the current traction,

¹ All documents from Open Call #1 will be available for download starting January 8, 2024, at www.empowomen.eu

implementation progress, and achievements of the project to gauge its present status and potential impact.

Impact: The Impact criteria focus on the future prospects of the proposal, evaluating the quality of the implementation plan that outlines the path forward. The business plan's realism and persuasiveness are examined, encompassing aspects such as market need and well-defined commercialization and market entry plans. The evaluators will also consider the growth potential in terms of turnover, profit, job creation, and broader economic impact. Additionally, the criteria assess the criticality of the grant to the company, examining its potential to make a significant difference and add substantial value. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) aspects associated with the proposed innovation are also taken into consideration.

Implementation: The Implementation criteria delve into the practical aspects of executing the proposed project. This includes evaluating the relevance of the female (co-)founder's role within the company, emphasizing leadership, decision-making, management capacity, and the ability to drive the company's success. The overall gender balance within the startup and the positions held by women are assessed for inclusivity. The team's skills, motivation, and commitment to project execution are scrutinized, ensuring they are well-equipped for the tasks at hand. The quality and efficiency of the work plan are also considered, examining the soundness of proposed activities and their necessity at the current stage of the project.

The evaluation will consist in an initial eligibility check, followed by a remote evaluation carried out with the support of external evaluators (Figure 1).

Eleven proposals will be selected and invited to the contract negotiation phase. An additional three proposals will be kept on a reserve list. All proposals will receive an acceptance or rejection letter together with an anonymised version of their Evaluation Summary Report (ESR).

At the end of the contract preparation and negotiation phase, the sub-grant agreement will be signed between the EmpoWomen consortium represented by its coordinator (SPLORO), and the Lead Beneficiary.

Figure 1. Evaluation process.

4. Attachments of the deliverable

As part of this deliverable, several attachments have been included to aid in the understanding of OC#1. These attachments are:

Annex 1 Guidelines for applicants

This document provides comprehensive instructions and details regarding the EmpoWomen Open Call #1. It likely includes information on eligibility criteria, application procedures, evaluation process, and any other essential guidelines for participants.

Annex 2 Application form

The application form is a reference document that applicants can consult before completing the official online form, which is available on the SPLORO platform. This form collects essential information about the startup, its founders, and its project. The form is a crucial part of the application process, and submissions are only accepted through online completion.

Annex 3 Leaflet

Promotional and informational document designed to provide a brief description of the EmpoWomen OC#1. The leaflets contain highlights, benefits, and key details about the OC#1 in a concise and visually appealing manner.

Annex 4 Open call announcement

This document is an official announcement that introduces and promotes EmpoWomen OC#1. It includes the purpose of the open call, key dates, and high-level information to attract potential applicants and stakeholders.

5. EmpoWomen Open Call #1

5.1 Introduction

The main goal of EmpoWomen is to create an exclusive support programme for female founders and entrepreneurs leading deep tech startups in the widening areas to grow into tomorrow's female tech leaders and to put women at the forefront of deep tech in Europe.

The primary objective of the EmpoWomen program is to boost the development of startups led by women in the digital and advanced technology sectors. This program is conceived as a strategic tool to foster female leadership in technological innovation, positioning women as essential players in the field of advanced technologies in Europe.

EmpoWomen aims to allocate 1.5 million EUR to achieve its objectives, attracting more than 150 applications with the aim of selecting 25 deserving startups.

These financial resources will be distributed across three components for the startups. Firstly, each beneficiary startup can receive up to 45,000 EUR in equity-free cash. Additionally, beneficiaries will be provided with a comprehensive acceleration program, including access to specialized mentoring, tailored training for the specific needs of startups, and participation in exclusive events. Vouchers facilitating access to key services such as acceleration, mentoring, and training, provided by external entities not affiliated with the beneficiary consortium, will be granted. Each startup can receive up to 12,400 EUR in vouchers. Finally, upon the conclusion of the acceleration program, a showcase event, the Demo Day, will be held where all startups will present their achievements. In this event, three prizes will be awarded to the top three startups, with a value of 15,000 EUR for the first place, 11,500 EUR for the second, and 6,000 EUR for the third. This ensures compliance with the conditions set forth in the call, stipulating that no startup can receive more than 60,000 EUR in FSTP funding.

The startups will be selected through two open calls to be launched in January 2024 and December 2024. Eligible beneficiaries will be startups led by women in deep tech, legally established in the Widening Area.

During the next 2 years (November 2023 - October 2025), the EmpoWomen consortium, comprised of 4 partners with 8 startup associations from the widening area, will join forces to make this a reality.

5.2 Background

EmpoWomen addresses the underrepresentation of women entrepreneurs in digital and deep tech in Europe. Despite constituting more than half of the population, women account for less than a third of entrepreneurs in the region. This project emerges as an innovative program to close the gender gap, foster collaboration between European ecosystems, and cultivate female leadership in advanced technology.

The European Commission recognizes the importance of female entrepreneurship as a source of economic growth and innovation. However, challenges persist, such as a lack of education and funding. In deep tech, women are underrepresented, resulting in low investment.

EmpoWomen presents itself as a bridge of continuity and improvement, led by SPLORO and supported by TechUkraine, BAE, and Startup Wise Guys. The goal is to create an exclusive support program for women-led startups in the widening area, using a structured pre-acceleration approach and offering additional assets in the form of vouchers. With a clear focus on women-led startups, EmpoWomen combines incentives into a single programme to empower future female leaders in technology.

5.3 Open call objectives

The purpose of EmpoWomen OC#1 is to actively involve women-led deep tech early-stage startups in the widening areas. This call seeks to identify and choose promising startups to participate in a customized acceleration programme. The overarching goal is to offer support that nurtures the development and investment potential of these startups, with the ultimate aim of cultivating them into leading female figures in deep tech innovation within Europe.

The objectives of EmpoWomen's open calls are as follows:

- To fund startups led by women in digital technology and deep tech in the countries of the European Union's widening area, providing up to 45,000 EUR in equity-free financing.
- To support the growth and development of these startups, helping them overcome initial financial barriers and progress on their path to success.
- To provide access to a network of mentors, networking opportunities, and other resources that strengthen the skills and business relationships of the entrepreneurs.
- To empower women entrepreneurs and increase the presence of startups led by women in the technology sector.

5.4 Open Call #1 Documentation

This section explains all the documentation that is an integral part of the OC#1, which has been made available to all applicants, is accessible on the [EmpoWomen website](#) and includes:

- [Guidelines for Applicants](#)
- [Annex 1. Application Form](#)
- [Annex 2. SME Declaration](#)
- [Annex 3. Sub-Grant Agreement](#)
- [FAQs document](#)

Guidelines for Applicants

Provides a detailed breakdown of the open call, including objectives, a description of the desired startups. It includes timeline, as well as details on the evaluation process, reporting and requirements for submitting a proposal.

Annex 1. Application Form

This document serves as a reference for the applicant to be aware of all the questions and required documents during the online application process through the Sploro platform.

Annex 2. SME declaration

This document is mandatory for all SMEs and provides information on the status of the SMEs.

Annex 3. Sub-Grant Agreement

Provides a template for the sub-grant agreement that selected startups are expected to sign with the lead beneficiary of the EmpoWomen project. It describes all the rights and responsibilities of the signing parties.

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) document

This document compiles common questions that prospective participants may have and provides clear and concise answers. Its goal is to guide applicants through the call, providing valuable information and eliminating potential uncertainties to facilitate a successful application process.

5.5 Funding Scheme

The EmpoWomen first open call dedicates 527,500 EUR to support women-led startups, providing equity-free funding of up to 45,000 EUR distributed gradually based on specific outcomes and milestones. Beyond the financial grant, the programme integrates mentoring, coaching, and networking for enhanced project success.

Three vouchers, valued at 5,000 EUR for events, 2,400 EUR for the business angels' investment readiness program, and 5,000 EUR for mentoring sessions, progressively unlock throughout the programme, offering additional resources for startup development, totaling 12,400 EUR.

As a culmination, the Demo Day, a showcase event at the end of the acceleration program, allows startups to present their accomplishments.

Prizes totaling 15,000 EUR for the first place, 11,500 EUR for the second, and 6,000 EUR for the third ensure adherence to the call's conditions, limiting FSTP funding to 60,000 EUR per startup.

5.6 Acceleration Programme Overview

The acceleration programme, led by Startup Wise Guys (SWG) and Business Angels Europe (BAE), spans six months and offers comprehensive support for startup growth.

The initial three months focus on key areas such as product development, sales strategies, pitching, legal considerations, and fundraising, all guided by SWG. A Progress Day at the end of this phase allows startups to showcase their progress to SWG and BAE.

The subsequent three months delve into in-depth fundraising guidance, exploring the fundraising process and receiving expert insights from BAE.

Throughout the entire journey, participants benefit from Mentoring Days, receiving tailored support from domain experts.

The programme culminates in a Demo Day at the end of the sixth month, where startups present to a curated audience of investors invited from programme partners' extensive networks.

This structured approach ensures a holistic and impactful journey for startup growth.

5.7 Open Call Timeline

The EmpoWomen Open Call #1 opens 8 January 2024 and closes on 8 March 2024 at 17:00 CET (Brussels time). Proposals must be submitted via the SPLORO Platform at https://bit.ly/EmpoWomen_OC1.

After submission, EmpoWomen will begin the evaluation and selection process (Figure 2). Proposals not fitting the eligibility criteria will be notified. The top eleven proposals will be invited to enter the contract preparation and signature phase and access the Acceleration Programme.

Figure 2. Timeline for submission, evaluation of proposals and acceleration programme for OC#1.

5.8 Additional information

All the information on the EmpoWomen project and open call is available on:

- The [project website](#), where all official documents are published.

- EmpoWomen social media channels: [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [Facebook](#).

Annex 1

Guidelines for Applicants

Prepared by: SPLORO

OPENING: 08 of January 2024

CLOSING: 08 of March 2024 at 17:00 CET

Project Website: www.empowomen.eu

Open Call platform: https://bit.ly/EmpoWomen_OC1

V1.0 26/12/2023

List of Acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
OC	Open Call
FSTP	Financial Support for Third Parties
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
VAT	Value Added Tax
ASA	Advance Subscription for Shares
SAFE	Simple Agreement for Future Equity

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	5
1.1 About EmpoWomen project	5
1.2 Objectives and ambition	6
2. Relevant dates	7
2.1 Applications	7
2.2 Evaluation	7
2.3 Acceleration Programme	8
3. Rules and conditions	9
3.1 Eligible Beneficiaries	9
3.2 Financial Support	12
3.2.1 Indicative distributions of the funds and Vouchers	13
3.2.2 Demo Day	14
3.3 Origin of Funds	14
3.4 Allocation of funds per project	15
3.5 Language	15
3.6 Documents format	15
3.7 Absence of conflict of interest	15
3.8 Ethical Issues	16
3.9 Data Protection	16
4. Proposal submission process	18
4.1 Overall process	18
4.2 Documents to be submitted	18
4.3 Application preparation	20
5. Proposal Evaluation and Selection Process	22
5.1 Application reception	22
5.2 Evaluation process	22
5.2.1 Eligibility criteria	22
5.2.2 Experts' remote evaluation	23

Annex 1. Guidelines for Applicants

5.2.3	Normalisation score	25
5.2.4	Interview stage.....	26
5.2.5	Final Selection	26
5.3	Appealing procedure.....	27
5.4	Validation of the legal entity	28
5.5	Sub-grant agreement preparation	29
6.	Acceleration Programme	30
7.	Beneficiaries' Responsibilities.....	35
7.1	Conflict of interest	35
7.2	Data protection and confidentiality	35
7.3	Promotion of the action and EU Funding visibility.....	35
7.4	Financial audits and control	37
7.5	Internal communication	37
7.6	External communication and open data	37

List of Figures

Figure 1.Lifecycle of a funded proposal	7
Figure 3. Evaluation process	22
Figure 2.Comprehensive 6-Month Startup Acceleration Journey.	30

List of Tables

Table 1. Payment milestones.....	13
Table 2. Criteria score	25

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this document, "**Guidelines for Applicants**," is to provide clear and concise instructions to applicants submitting proposals for the first open call of the EmpoWomen project (**OC#1**), **which opens on January 8, 2024, and closes on March 8, 2024**, coinciding with **International Women's Day**. The document contains information that is specific to this deadline, including eligibility criteria, evaluation procedures, and submission requirements, which have been carefully curated to ensure clarity and accuracy. **It is important to note that the information presented in this document may not apply to the next call launched by the EmpoWomen project.** (The next call, which will be in December 2024, will have its own guidelines). Therefore, it is essential that all applicants thoroughly read and comprehend this document to ensure that their proposals meet the specific requirements outlined for the OC#1.

The Guidelines for Applicants document aims to assist potential applicants for the EmpoWomen OC#1. It is provided for information purposes only and is not intended to replace **consultation of the Sub-Grant Agreement template (Annex 3)**, where it is defined the framework of rights and obligations of the Contracting Parties for the development of the financed project. The Sub-Grant Agreement will be signed by the EmpoWomen coordinator, on behalf of the entire consortium, and each beneficiary of this open call.

1.1 About EmpoWomen project.

EmpoWomen funded by the European Union through its Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme, seeks to overcome the obstacles faced by women in the field of R&D&I to improve equality in deep tech entrepreneurship.

Despite consistent growth in the business world, women remain substantially underrepresented as entrepreneurs, particularly in Europe. In the deep tech sector, currently valued at 700 billion EUR, women account for only 10% of patent applications, and less than 15% of startups are founded or co-founded by women.

EmpoWomen offers a unique programme for scaling up women-led companies with the objective to create an exclusive support programme for female founders and entrepreneurs leading deep tech startups from widening-area countries to grow into tomorrow's female tech leaders and put women at the forefront of deep tech in the world.

The initiative EmpoWomen is a 2-year programme (2024-2025) which consists of a unique acceleration and mentoring programme and includes non-repayable funding totaling 1,125 M EUR, prizes and services to 25 women-led deep-tech companies selected through a competitive process from European emerging markets and the outermost regions and associated EU countries.

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Sploro, TechUkraine, Business Angels Europe (BAE) and Startup Wise Guys (SWG), all together with 8 startup associations from the widening area will run this innovative programme which will be the first to support deep tech women-led companies. The selected women-led businesses will each have access to a 6-month programme consisting of a dedicated acceleration and investment readiness support service by SWG, webinars and events, together with specialist training and mentoring from Business Angels, combined with Demo days and direct connections with both Angel Investors and Venture capitals (VCs), offering the potential to access investment.

1.2 Objectives and ambition

The purpose of EmpoWomen_OC#1 is to actively involve women-led deep tech early-stage startups in the widening areas. This call seeks to identify and choose promising startups to participate in a customized acceleration programme. The overarching goal is to offer support that nurtures the development and investment potential of these startups, with the ultimate aim of cultivating them into leading female figures in deep tech innovation within Europe.

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2. Relevant dates

Figure 1. Lifecycle of a funded proposal

2.1 Applications

Opening: **08.01.2024**

Deadline for submission: **08.03.2024, 17:00h CET**

2.2 Evaluation

- **Evaluation period:** Indicatively period to evaluate applicants. **11.03.2024 to 05.04.2024**
- **Interviews:** only the applicants who passed the evaluation stage will be interviewed. Applicants will be called for one interview time slot among the following dates: **08.04.2024 to 12.04.2024 and 15.04.2024 to 19.04.2024**. Rejecting or failing to attend the interview will disqualify the applicant without further due.
- **Results:** The publication of the evaluation's final results will be around **25.04.24**, marking the beginning of the contract signing process and the inclusion of successful candidates into the programme. There will not be any prior disclosure of information about the evaluation process before that date.
- **Legal validation and Sub-grant agreement preparation:** starting from **25.04.2024 to 03.05.2024**. Legal validation is applied exclusively to successful applicants and involves the submission of various documents (**see Section 5.4**) to ensure compliance with the requirements of the EmpoWomen programme. Successful applicants will begin preparation for the Sub-grant agreement signature until **03.05.2024**.

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2.3 Acceleration Programme

- **Onboarding:** Starting from **06.05.2024**, the selected teams will commence identifying the most suitable range of services for their training during the programme.

To learn more details about the acceleration program, you can refer to **Section 6** of this document.

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3. Rules and conditions

3.1 Eligible Beneficiaries

EmpoWomen primarily focuses on women-led deep tech early-stage startups in Widening Areas. In this section, specific criteria and conditions are outlined, establishing eligibility for potential beneficiaries. EmpoWomen offers a personalized programme that provides you with access to high-level acceleration services, equity-free financing, and vouchers for business support services.

To be eligible as an applicant at EmpoWomen, it is essential to understand certain key criteria that define the profile of a qualified beneficiary. Here are the key definitions that guide the selection of beneficiaries:

1. **Startup:** a 'start-up' should be understood as an SME, according to the EU definition of SMEs, in the early stage of its life cycle, including those that are created as spin-offs from university research activities, which aims to find innovative solutions and scalable business models, and which is autonomous within the meaning of [Article 2 and 3 of the Annex to Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC](#).
2. **Early-stage startup:** For the purpose of the project, we would consider the following criteria to define an early-stage start-up:
 - companies that have been established and operating for not more than 6 years counting backwards from submission date and,
 - companies that have raised limited funding (up to 1 M EUR).
3. **Women Leadership Criterion:** The startup's leadership must have a substantial representation of women, and it is crucial that at least one woman assumes a key role, whether as a co-founder, a member of the core management team, or serving on the board of directors. While acknowledging the inclusion of women on the board, it is important to highlight that this criterion alone may not fulfill the requirement. Board members should not only be representatives from incubators, accelerators, or venture capital firms but must also demonstrate a significant connection to the project or the founding team.
4. **Female Founder or Co-founder Requirement:** The project aims to support women in their diverse forms, encompassing cisgender and transgender women legally recognized as such. The eligibility for the founding or co-founding requirement is met if the woman is legally acknowledged as the founder or co-founder of the company in a Widening Area region. Applicants are expected to provide evidence of their status as founders or co-founders.

Note: women leadership criterion as well as female founder or co-founder requirement are both compulsory

5. **Deep tech:** The startup must be engaged in the development of advanced and disruptive technologies. According to the EU regulation: "Deep tech is technology that is based on

cutting-edge scientific advances and discoveries and is characterised by the need to stay at the technological forefront by constant interaction with new ideas and results from the lab. Deep tech innovation aims to provide concrete solutions to our societal problems by finding its source in a deep interaction with the most recent scientific and technological advances and by seeking to produce a profound impact in the targeted application technologies.”¹

Deep Tech Technologies

In the context of OC#1 of the EmpoWomen project, relevance is given to various deep tech technologies where women play a fundamental role. These deep tech technologies, carefully selected for the call, span from quantum computing to emerging technologies such as augmented reality and artificial intelligence.

The call will encompass the following deep tech technologies:

- **Advanced Computing /Quantum Computing:** Advanced Computing involves the use of cutting-edge technologies to perform complex computations at high speeds, while Quantum Computing leverages principles of quantum mechanics to process information using quantum bits (qubits), potentially revolutionizing computing capabilities beyond classical limitations.
- **Advanced Manufacturing:** The technologies in this area are diverse and include, but are not limited to, the following categories. There are also overlaps with other technologies listed separately, including Robotics, AI/ML; VR/AR; 5G; Digital Twins; Robotics; Edge Computing.
- **Advanced Materials:** The research, development, engineering and production of advanced materials with engineered properties, including ceramics, high value-added metals, electronic materials, composites, polymers, and biomaterials.
- **Aerospace, Automotive and Remote Sensing:** This technological area focusses on new methods of transport and mobility and space technology as well as the sensing, data and telecommunications processing systems required for successful innovation.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, including Big Data:** This technological area focusses on the interaction between data science, Big Data and data mining as well as the methods used to process data via algorithms and other learning methods into specific use cases.

¹ European Innovation Council (EIC) Work Programme 2023 https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2023/wp_horizon-eic-2023_en.pdf

- **Biotechnology and Life Sciences:** Biotechnology and life sciences represents cutting edge Deep Tech technology in terms of natural and synthetic materials and research, including genetic therapies and digital technologies.
- **Communications and Networks, including 5G:** Communications and connectivity in terms of Deep Tech refers to research and innovation in areas such as 5G / 6G Networks, Navigation Systems, Telematics and Materials and Communications Security.
- **Cybersecurity and Data Protection:** This area focusses on the application of Deep Tech technologies to network and data security and protection. This includes the trustworthiness and certification of ICT products: Internet of Things (IoT) and 5G, Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), Encryption Systems and Methods, Intrusion Detection Systems and Methods and Privacy-Enhancing Technologies and Methods.
- **Electronics and Photonics:** The Deep Tech technological dimension of electronics and photonics typically refers to technology used in Quantum Computing as well as Semiconductor manufacturing. There are a wide range of technological applications that include, but are not limited to: Quantum Computing, Microelectronics / Circuit Board Engineering, Photonic Engineering, Haptic, AI and VR/AR Engineering and Power Management.
- **Internet of Things, W3C, Semantic Web:** This Deep Tech technological area focusses on the physical and network systems for Internet of Things; the communications protocols and data structure for embedded and interconnected devices and systems.
- **Robotics:** Robotics includes development of hardware and software solutions for process and machine automation.
- **Semiconductors (microchips):** In addition to the scientific frontiers of semiconductor research, recent policy concerns incorporates re-onshoring or security of supply of semiconductor production. Deep Tech areas of interest include, but are not limited to: Advanced Microchip Manufacturing Methods, Other Microchip Applications, Non-Conventional Computing Systems and Semiconductors, Haptic, AI and VR/AR Engineering, Power Management and Environmental Health and Safety / Circularity.
- **Sustainable Energy and Clean Technologies:** Sustainable Energy focuses on renewable and environmentally friendly energy sources, while Clean Technologies involve the development of solutions that minimize environmental impact and promote sustainable practices.
- **Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, Metaverse:** This technological area focusses on the creation and application of digital information and content, either in a partial or fully-immersive environment. Examples include, but are not limited to: Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Metaverse and Other Advanced Digital Applications and Hardware.

- **Web 3.0, including Blockchain, Distributed Ledgers, NFTs:** This technological area focusses on Web 3.0 applications insofar as these relate to solving a major societal challenge. Examples include, but are not limited to Web 3.0, Blockchain and NFT.

Applicants are advised that, in a subsequent phase following the evaluation process, if selected, they will be asked to complete an Ethics Self-Assessment. This step is crucial to ensure ethical compliance in the areas of research and development. Full cooperation is expected from the chosen startup in this regard.

6. **Companies located in the list of eligible countries and regions:** Only applicants legally established in any of the following countries (hereafter collectively identified as the “Eligible Countries”) are eligible for funding:
 - **Widening Area Countries:** Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Estonia, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia.
 - **Outermost regions:** Guadeloupe, French Guiana, Réunion, Martinique, Mayotte and Saint-Martin (France), Canary Islands (Spain), Guadeloupe, French Guiana, Réunion, Martinique, Mayotte and Saint-Martin (France).
 - **Associated countries:** Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, North Macedonia, Georgia, Moldova, Montenegro, Serbia, Tunisia, Turkey and Ukraine.

Should the definition of Widening Area be updated by the European Union institutions our restrictions may change. The valid list will be the existing one at the time of the closure of the call.

3.2 Financial Support

The first call boasts a total budget of 527,500 EUR. Beyond the financial grant, EmpoWomen extends support through mentoring, coaching, and networking opportunities, fostering an environment conducive to achieving project objectives.

In this OC#1, EmpoWomen is committed to providing equity-free funding to empower **up to 11 startups** led by women. Additionally, the programme incorporates three distinct vouchers aimed at enhancing the entrepreneurial journey. These vouchers encompass coverage for participation in EU tech summits, access to a dedicated mentor for the company, and an exclusive programme on business angels' investment, facilitated directly by seasoned angel investors with relevant expertise and geographical alignment.

The grant is disbursed over the course of the EmpoWomen project, following a "flat rate" approach. This means that the funding is distributed gradually, subject to meeting specific outcomes and milestones, rather than administrative justifications of time and/or expenses.

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3.2.1 Indicative distributions of the funds and Vouchers

Payments and vouchers will be distributed in multiple stages throughout the project's timeline, subject to the achievement of specified milestones or key performance indicators and the attainment of specific results. All of these disbursements operate in parallel with the execution of the acceleration program (**section 6**).

Table 1. Payment milestones

Project Duration	Month 1	Month 3	Month 6
	Coaching Plan & KPIs definition	MID-TERM REVIEW	FINAL REVIEW
Output	D1. Individual Programme KPIs	Participate in at least 80% of the project acceleration activities until month 3.	Achievement of established KPIs for month 6.
		Achievement of established KPIs for month 3.	All the payments will be held to those teams who have engaged with less than 75% of the program content during the 6 months Participation of the startups in the final demo day.
Grant per Team (€)	5,000 EUR	20,000 EUR	20,000 EUR
Vouchers	Vouchers will be unlocked progressively during the programme. Startups will be allowed to request the voucher depending on the expertise and the stage of the programme reached.		

Payments will be done at beginning of the months following the output deliverables. (Beginning of M2, Months 4 and Months 7)

- **Voucher 1. Access to Events:** Covering expenses for attending EU tech summits. Participation in at least 2 events per startup. The events (different from the Demo Day) will be communicated by the EmpoWomen consortium during the execution of the acceleration program. **Valued at 5,000 EUR per startup.**
- **Voucher 2. Business Angels (BA) Investment Readiness Programme:** Dedicated programme on business angels' investment provided directly by real angel investors who have an overlap within their expertise/geography. **Valued at 2,400 EUR per startup.**

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Annex 1. Guidelines for Applicants

- **Voucher 3. Mentoring:** up to 16 sessions of a dedicated mentor for the company. **Valued at 5,000 EUR per startup.**

Vouchers will be directly paid by EmpoWomen consortium to the providers of services (events, mentors, etc.) The value of the vouchers is added on top of the cash received by the startups, never deducted.

Projects will be paid according to their overall completion of KPIs. Only in the case of an underperformance below 25% the team will be disqualified, and no further payment released. Regarding payments, the beneficiary must comply with a series of rules and conditions that can be found in greater detail in the Sub-Grant Agreement [\(Annex 3\)](#).

3.2.2 Demo Day

The **Demo Day**, a crucial event at the end of the programme, will provide beneficiaries with the opportunity to showcase their startups to programme mentors and external judges. On this day, the EmpoWomen Awards Ceremony will take place, where the performance and potential of the startups will be assessed. **It is important to note that the attendance of all beneficiaries is mandatory to ensure their eligibility for the final payment.** The top three startups, selected during this event, will receive project prizes based on their ranking.

- **Prize 1:** 15,000 EUR
- **Prize 2:** 11,500 EUR
- **Prize 3:** 6,000 EUR

3.3 Origin of Funds

Once an applicant has been selected for funding, they will be required to sign a dedicated Sub-Grantee Funding Agreement with the EmpoWomen consortium. It is important to note that the funds attached to the Sub-Grantee Funding Agreement come directly from the funds of the Horizon Europe Project EmpoWomen, which has been funded by the European Commission. Therefore, the funds remain the property of the EU until the payment of the balance, which is managed by the project partners in EmpoWomen via European Commission Horizon Europe Grant Agreement Number 101120693.

The Sub-Grantee Funding Agreement represents a significant commitment from both the EmpoWomen programme and the sub-grantees who will receive funding. The relationship between sub-grantees and the European Commission through the EmpoWomen programme carries a set of obligations for the sub-grantees with the European Commission. These obligations will be outlined in the Sub-Grantee Agreement, which the selected applicants will need to review and agree to. It is the responsibility of the sub-grantees to ensure that they fulfil these obligations, and the EmpoWomen consortium partners will provide guidance and support as needed.

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All selected applicants should carefully review the terms of the agreement and ensure that they are able to meet their obligations in order to receive the funding and successfully carry out their project.

3.4 Allocation of funds per project.

The financing provided for each sub-granted project is determined through a lump sum scheme, taking into account the requirements specified in the call text and the duration of the programme.

The total funding limit for a single organization across all EmpoWomen calls is set at **60,000 EUR**. An organization could only reach this maximum amount if it receives the 45,000 EUR grant upon completing the entire programme and emerges as the winner of the first prize, securing an additional 15,000 EUR at the Demo Day.

EmpoWomen will have a total of two calls, where up to 25 startups will benefit. The goal is to select up to 11 startups for the OC#1 and 14 for the second open call. Therefore, for this initial call, the total available budget is 527,500 EUR. The number of startups chosen per call may vary. If there are not enough projects financed in the first call until the available budget is exhausted, the remaining budget will be allocated to the second open call.

3.5 Language

English is the official language for the EmpoWomen open calls. Submissions done in any language other than English will not be eligible or evaluated.

English is the only official language during the whole implementation of the EmpoWomen programme. This means that any requested submission of documentation and deliverables will be done in English to be eligible, and the programme activities will be only held in English.

3.6 Documents format

Any documentation requested in any of the phases of the open call and programmes' implementation must be submitted electronically in PDF format without restrictions for printing.

3.7 Absence of conflict of interest

Applicants must not have any actual or potential conflicts of interest during the EmpoWomen selection process or the entire project duration. Any situations that could potentially influence

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the impartiality of the individuals taking part in the selection process, or during the project implementation, are considered conflicts of interest. These can include financial interests, personal relationships, or any other factors that could affect the applicant's ability to remain impartial. All cases of conflict of interest will be assessed on a case-by-case basis by the relevant EmpoWomen selection committee and consortium partners. **If an applicant is found to have a conflict of interest, this could result in the application being disqualified.**

It is important to note that **EmpoWomen consortium partners, their affiliated entities, employees, and permanent co-operators are not allowed to submit a proposal and therefore to receive any financial support through the open calls**, as this would violate the European Commission's regulations.

3.8 Ethical Issues

EmpoWomen strictly adheres to the fundamental ethical principles outlined in the "European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity." To ensure compliance, all applicants are required to acknowledge and accept our privacy policy and declaration of honor (ethics) during the submission process. This acknowledgment confirms that, by submitting the form, they accept the terms described in the provided text. No additional documents need to be uploaded; applicants are solely required to read and agree to the terms outlined when submitting the form.

During the evaluation process, **the EmpoWomen consortium may verify whether the self-assessment declaration aligns with the contents of the application.** In cases where clarification is needed, the consortium reserves the right to contact the beneficiaries. If an applicant indicates that their application may have ethical issues, an ethics review will be conducted. Applications that fail to adequately address ethical concerns or privacy aspects will be rejected.

All applicants must thoroughly review and assess their applications for any potential ethical issues before submission. **Failure to comply with the ethical guidelines outlined in the "European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity" could lead to disqualification of the application.** Therefore, it is of utmost importance that all applicants take the necessary steps to ensure that their proposals meet the highest ethical standards.

3.9 Data Protection

EmpoWomen requires access to Personal and Entity Data in order to process and evaluate applications. As open call coordinator, SPLORO will act as the Data Controller for all data submitted through the Sploro platform for this purpose. To ensure the safety and security of this data, the Sploro platform has been designed and operates under strict compliance with The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). Therefore, all applicants are required to accept the

Annex 1. Guidelines for Applicants

Sploro Platform terms to ensure full coverage. For more information regarding the data privacy policy and security measures implemented by Sploro, please refer to their website at <https://sploro.eu>.

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4. Proposal submission process

4.1 Overall process

The submission will be done through the official online submission platform, which is directly linked to the EmpoWomen website. Only applications received directly through the online submission platform will be considered eligible.

We will provide applicants with an editable template of the application form ([see Annex 1](#)) to let them prepare the application offline before introducing the information in the form available at the Sploro platform. **Sending this form template in any other format and via e-mail or any other means will automatically disqualify the submission.**

If the applicant discovers an error in a submitted application or aims to improve the application, the applicant may submit a new version provided the call deadline has not passed. For this, the applicant must get in touch with the managers of the open call (SPLORO) at EmpoWomen to reopen the application through the support channel. Applicants will be able to modify all answers of the application form as many times as needed until the deadline. Please be aware that once opened, the applicants should send the form again, or it will not be evaluated. Once resubmitted, only the last version received before the call deadline will be considered in the evaluation.

EmpoWomen offers a dedicated **support channel** available for applicants at helpdesk@empowomen.eu. Requests will receive a response within 72 hours of their submission. While all possible effort will be made to respond in a timely manner, the teams should plan their submission accordingly, allowing enough time before the deadline (i.e., at least 72 hours prior) if they expect an answer.

Please note that any email received outside the designated support channel will not be taken into account. It is imperative that all requests or inquiries related to the submission system or the call itself are directed through the official support channel. Requests or inquiries received AFTER two days before the closure time of the call will neither be considered nor answered. Lack of receipt of an answer to an inquiry shall not constitute grounds for an extension or re-evaluation of a submission.

4.2 Documents to be submitted

The application process will be exclusively through the **SPLORO platform**. Before you begin, we recommend carefully reviewing [Annex 1](#), a preliminary version of the form, to familiarize yourself with key elements.

Annex 1. Guidelines for Applicants

The application process is structured into sections designed to evaluate the **excellence, impact, and implementation**. External evaluators, experts in various fields, will use these criteria to select the most promising projects.

All required documents, such as the SME Declaration ([Annex 2](#)), CVs, and the Pitch Deck, must be uploaded **in PDF format** through the SPLORO platform.

[Application form](#): an online form divided in different sections:

1) Legal and Contact Information:

- Collects essential participant and organization details.
- Captures eligibility information, legal status, and registration details.
- Designates a contact point within the organization.

2) Project Description:

- Outlines core activities, addressing a specific problem.
- Identifies the deep tech technologies targeted.
- Assesses the solution's readiness level and ownership of intellectual property.

3) **Excellence:**

- Addresses objectives in the EmpoWomen call.
- Highlights technological innovation, advancements, and uniqueness.
- Explores collaborations, achievements, and scientific or technical progress.

4) **Impact:**

- Details business overview, target market, and competitors.
- Identifies barriers to entry and strategies to overcome them.
- Describes potential customers, business model, and fundraising plans.

5) **Implementation:**

- Profiles key team members, emphasizing gender equity and diversity.
- Explores team's deep tech industry experience and achievements.
- Covers the female founder's active participation and previous startup experience.

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6) Areas of Interest for Acceleration Programme:

- Seeks insights into specific areas where the startup would benefit.
- Covers product development, sales, pitching, legal considerations, fundraising, and other areas.

7) Privacy Policy:

- Ensures understanding and compliance with open call details.
- Confirms correctness and completeness of information.
- Asserts eligibility and absence of conflict of interest.

8) Declaration of Honour:

- Certifies accuracy, completeness, and compliance.
- Commits to participation, stable funding, and necessary resources.
- Declares no administrative sanctions, exclusion situations, or conflicts of interest.

Applicants must strictly adhere to the form provided by EmpoWomen consortium via Sploro platform, which defines sections and the overall length. Evaluators will be instructed not to consider extra material in the evaluation.

4.3 Application preparation

For the successful submission, applicants are strongly advised to follow these steps:

1. Check the guidelines for applicants to determine if your organisation is eligible for the programme.
2. Applicants are required to apply online and answer all mandatory questions (with no exception) at: https://bit.ly/EmpoWomen_OC1. Moreover, applicants must submit all the requested documents established in the call. The lack of any of the documents will negatively affect the eligibility of the applicant for the evaluation process. In addition, note that certain documents - which will be required for each applicant selected for the programme and signing a sub-grantee agreement - may take time to acquire. It is highly

advisable that you read the **Section 5.5: Sub-grant agreement preparation** and take into consideration the time needed to obtain these documents.

3. Be concrete and concise. Open questions have character limitations. Please examine all the open call documents and attend at least one of the online events promoted by the EmpoWomen programme to be prepared. Please, mark your calendars for our upcoming InfoDays:
 - **1st InfoDay:** January 17, 2024
 - **2nd InfoDay:** February 15, 2024
4. Only the submission within the Open Call duration will be accepted. There will not be any deadline extensions unless there is a Force Majeure situation (i.e., a major problem with the platform caused by the EmpoWomen consortium and not by the applicants, making the system unavailable for a long period). It is strongly advised not to wait until the last minute.

5. Proposal Evaluation and Selection Process

5.1 Application reception

Submissions will be done ONLY via the [Sploro platform](#), and it will be the unique entry point for all application submissions. Applications submitted by any other means will not be considered nor evaluated. Only the documentation included in the submission will be considered by evaluators. A full list of applicants will be drafted containing their basic information for statistical purposes and clarity (which will be also shared with the EC for transparency). The application reception will close on **08.03.2024, 17:00 CET**. There will not be any deadline extensions unless there is a Force Majeure situation, caused by the EmpoWomen consortium and not by the applicants, which renders the system unavailable.

5.2 Evaluation process

The evaluation process to be followed during the selection of the applicants is shown in the following figure. Before entering into the programme, a three-step evaluation will take place:

Figure 2. Evaluation process

The evaluation process will be evaluated according to the following categories:

5.2.1 Eligibility criteria

An automatic filtering to discard non-eligible proposals will follow the shortlist below. Eligibility criteria check will verify:

- All the required fields in the online application form have been completed and all documents are uploaded.
- The startup is a 'deep tech' company.
- The start-up is founded or co-founded by women holding a top management position (CEO, CTO or equivalent) in the company at the time of submission.
- The existence of a legal entity.

- e) Registration of the company before the opening of the call and with less than 6 years since registration (deadline date set by submission deadline)
- f) Company classification as SME. A SME will be considered as such if complying with the European Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC¹⁶ and, the SME user guide¹⁷. In a summary, the criteria which define an SME are:
 - o Independent (not linked or owned by another enterprise), by Recommendation 2003/361/EC.
 - o Headcount in Annual Work Unit (AWU) less than 250.
 - o Annual turnover less or equal to 50 million EUR OR annual balance sheet total less or equal to 43 million EUR.
- g) Having raised less than 1M EUR in equity or public funding until submission date.
- h) The uniqueness of the proposal (proposal not already funded in the Women TechEU initiative and/or any other identical project to avoid double funding).
- i) Companies located in the list of eligible countries or regions.

Applications marked as non-eligible will get a rejection letter including the reasons (a to i) for being declared as non-eligible. No further feedback on the process will be given.

5.2.2 Experts' remote evaluation

The proposals that pass the eligibility check will move to the remote evaluation stage. Applications will be assessed by a group of external and independent evaluators with an entrepreneurial, investment or innovation background. The evaluators will assess the proposals based on 3 different evaluation criteria (**Excellence, Impact and Implementation**).

- 1) **Excellence**: projects must demonstrate high quality and a clear set of objectives aligned with the EmpoWomen vision and with the general objectives of the project. The Excellence is evaluated according to the following criteria:
 - a) Alignment of the application with the call and the EIC accelerator [criteria](#);
 - b) Degree of deep-tech innovation (i.e., going beyond the state-of-the-art, chances to succeed, its feasibility);
 - c) Current traction/implementation/achievements of the project.
- 2) **Impact**: The impact is evaluated according to the following criteria:
 - a) The quality of the future implementation plan;

- b) Business plan (i.e., whether it is realistic and convincing, whether the applicant demonstrated market need and willingness to pay, as well as commercialisation plan and market entry plan);
 - c) The growth potential of the proposed innovation/solution in terms of turnover, profit, and jobs, as well as its broader economic impact;
 - d) How critical this grant is for the company, and whether it will make a difference and add value to the company.
 - e) IPR aspects.
- 3) **Implementation:** The implementation is evaluated according to the following criteria:
- a) Relevance of the female (co-)founder role in the company (i.e., whether the woman (co-)founder has a leading role in the company, whether she is the decision-maker, whether she has a management capacity and whether she can bring the company to the next level);
 - b) An overall gender balance and the position held by women in the start-up;
 - c) Team's skills, motivation, and commitment to execute the project;
 - d) Quality and efficiency of the work plan (i.e., whether the proposed activities are sound and well explained, as well as whether these activities are most needed at this stage).

The selected evaluators will be independent of the organisations involved in the consortium and of any third party applying to the call. The evaluators will sign a declaration of confidentiality concerning the contents of the proposals they read. The form which they use in the evaluation carries a declaration of freedom from conflict of interest which they agree to by signing them. Proposals will be evaluated by 2 independent evaluators. All evaluators will receive the evaluation guidelines, templates, and will be duly informed about the timing for an agile process and conflict of interest issues.

The evaluators will score each award criterion on a scale from 0 to 5:

Table 2. Criteria score

Score	Definition
0	Proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information.
1	Poor – criterion is inadequately addressed or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
2	Fair – proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses
3	Good – proposal addresses the criterion well, but a number of shortcomings are present.
4	Very good- proposal addresses the criterion very well, but a small number of shortcomings are present.
5	The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

The total score will be calculated as an average of the score of the 3 different criteria. **The threshold for each criterion will be three (3), while the overall score threshold will be ten (10).** That means if a proposal receives less than 3 in one criterion or less than 10 overall score, will not be recommended for funding by the independent evaluators and will be automatically rejected.

5.2.3 Normalisation score

For the final grade calculation, there will be two evaluators per proposal, where each one will score differently without knowing the evaluation of their colleague, thus avoiding one evaluator conditioning the other. Therefore, the same evaluation may receive very different scores.

The normalisation process counts with a several steps approach:

- **External Evaluators Average (EEA) and Overall Average Score (OAS):** each evaluator has evaluated several proposals. We calculate the average score of all applicants and compare it with the average score of each evaluator.
- Each External Evaluator Average is compared to the Overall Average Score using a simple division (EEA / OAS). As a result, we know the percentage each evaluator represents of the OAS. This has a double meaning:

- Evaluators under 100% have a negative pattern against the average. Their scores are then increased.
- Evaluators above 100% have a positive pattern against the average. Their scores are then decreased.
- **Correction factor:** Based on this formula $1 + (1 - (EEA/OAS))$. This factor is unique for each evaluator.
- The following step is applying the Correction Factor to each criterion per evaluator. **Excellence x Correction Factor | Impact x Correction factor | Implementation x Correction factor.**
- Then we calculate the final score of each criterion as the average of each corrected score of the two evaluators on each proposal. (It may be the case that correction brings scores over a 5 in any criteria. In those cases, the score is capped in 5).
- We add the corrected scores and calculate the total score.
- Finally, we build the shortlist according from highest to lowest total score.

Using this method, a more balanced distribution of scores would be guaranteed, and the possibility of biases and distortions would be reduced. At the end of the evaluation process, all proposals will be ranked based on their scores. The list of accepted proposals at remote evaluation will be published as well as the information about the non-eligible proposals. All applicants will be informed about the evaluation results.

5.2.4 Interview stage

The top-ranked projects of the external remote evaluation shall be duly invited to participate in an online interview. Given that the interview will be recorded, utmost consideration shall be accorded to data protection throughout the process. **The interview aims to deeply understand project concepts, team skills & competence.** At least 2 external evaluators will carry out the interviews.

The evaluation of this stage will be simple. The 2 evaluators will determine individually if the proposal they are interviewing should move forward with a yes/no decision. Each yes decision will motivate an extra 1 point in the overall evaluation and a new shortlist list will be populated.

At the end of the evaluation process all proposals will be ranked based on their scores (15 points from remote evaluation + 2 points from interview maximum).

5.2.5 Final Selection

At the end of the evaluation process all proposals will be ranked based on their scores, and the best proposals will be invited to sign the sub-grant agreement ([Annex 3](#)) and participate in the programme. The list of accepted proposals at remote evaluation will be published as well as the

information about the noneligible proposals. All applicants will be informed about the evaluation results.

The criteria for the ranking of the proposals will be semi-automatic following the rules below:

- **Rule 1:** The proposals will be ranked based on their overall score.
- **Rule 2:** In case following Rule 1 there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have higher score on the Excellence & Impact award criterion.
- **Rule 3:** In case following Rule 2 there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have a higher score on the 3 Implementation and Use of resources of the proposed team innovation award criterion.
- **Rule 4:** In case following Rule 3 there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to the total number of women in the team.

The EmpoWomen consortium will then formally approve a list of proposals within the limits of the available funding.

Prior to contracting to the top ranked applicants, the consortium will ask for the approval of the European Commission, and the list of selected projects will be submitted to the European Commission for final screening. Once validated, the project will communicate the results and every applicant will receive via email: An Evaluation Summary Report (ESR) and a letter informing of the rejection decision or invitation to negotiation and following steps.

5.3 Appealing procedure

The EmpoWomen consortium has established a process that allows applicants to appeal the decision of the consortium in the event their proposal is not selected for funding. If, at any point during the evaluation process, an applicant believes that there has been a deficiency in how their proposal was assessed, which could potentially impact the final funding decision, or if they believe that the results of eligibility checks are incorrect and do not adhere to the Open Call rules, resulting in harm to their interests, the following appeal procedure is available.

- If clear evidence of a deficiency that could influence the ultimate funding decision exists, it is possible that all or part of the proposal will be subject to re-evaluation.
- Complaints must be submitted within **five (calendar) days** from the date of receiving the evaluation results.
- As a general guideline, the EmpoWomen Team will investigate complaints with the aim of reaching a decision to issue a formal notice or to close the case within no more than **twenty days from the date of receiving the complaint**, provided that all required information has been submitted by the complainant.

- In cases where this time limit is exceeded, the EmpoWomen team will inform the complainant via email. If a definitive response cannot be provided at that stage, the response will indicate when a definitive response will be furnished.
- It should be noted that the EmpoWomen consortium does not commit to engage in any further discussion regarding the evaluation of a proposal beyond the definitive response.

Please be aware that only one request for appeal per proposal will be considered by the consortium.

5.4 Validation of the legal entity

Before validating the final list of accepted applicants, we will perform a thorough validation of the legal entities. This validation includes the submission of various documents to ensure compliance with the EmpoWomen programme's requirements. The requested elements for validation that will be requested are:

- For entities that are already validated by the European Commission's Funding and Tenders Portal that count with a registered and validated PIC Number we will request the PIC Number and a screenshot of the Funding and Tenders portal in which it's evidenced the type of organisation which has been selected as a beneficiary (university, NGO, foundation, SME...)

For those entities without a validated PIC number OR without a validated status (like self- declared SMEs) we will request:

- **Legal entity form.** The Legal Entity form for [private companies](#), and [public law bodies](#) necessary for the awarding of EU funding. Company Register, Official Journal and so forth, showing the name of the organisation, the legal address and registration number and
- **VAT Number registration** (if applicable), a copy of a document proving VAT registration (in case the VAT number does not show on the registration extract or its equivalent).
- **SME declaration** ([see Annex 2](#)): form based on the standard templates by the EC in which the consortium can verify the ownership structure and financial figures to verify the size of the company.
- Balance accounts and P&L for the last two closed years (if applicable)
- In companies with linked or associated entities, additional information (accounts for mother companies, group trees, etc.) could be requested.

A legal entity that does not provide the requested data and documents in due time will not be included in EmpoWomen Programme.

5.5 Sub-grant agreement preparation

After the validation of the Legal Entity, a written Sub-grantee agreement will be signed with successful applicants, and the EmpoWomen coordinator will request the applicant to fill a Financial Identification Form (FIF).

- **Sub-grantee funding agreement ([Annex 3](#)).** Signed between the Consortium (represented by the coordinator SPLORO) and the beneficiary.
- **Financial Identification Form (FIF).** Form identifying the account to which the funds will be transferred signed by the legal representative of the organisation and including a bank statement showing the ownership of the account. The coordinator of the consortium, SPLORO, will also provide additional security measures to verify the ownership of the account.
- All the legal issues are accurately covered by the planned contracts with the sub-granted beneficiaries. The sub-grant agreement will foresee, among other things, the special clauses derived from Horizon Europe in cascading granting, the payment schedule, and conditions (milestones), general legal text issues of rights and obligations by the EmpoWomen consortium and each sub-grantee, including IPR. It will also have a set of annexes such as the description of the project, the Financial Identification Form and any other document required by EmpoWomen consortium to assure the correct execution of the sub-granted projects.

The sub-granted projects will also define in the Individual Mentoring Plan their coaching plan and their research, business, and milestones linked to a set of KPIs, to which the project will associate the payment at the end of each phase. The objective of the contract preparation is fulfilling the legal requirements between the EmpoWomen consortium and every beneficiary of the call.

After signing the sub-grant agreement, beneficiaries will be eligible to participate in the Empowomen Acceleration Program.

6. Acceleration Programme

This unique **EmpoWomen Accelerator** offers a 6-month programme of dedicated intensive support to the selected group of women deep tech entrepreneurs, with a view to enabling them to significantly boost their business growth and increase their potential to access investment.

The **EmpoWomen Accelerator Programme** is delivered by two leading European players:

- **StartUp Wise Guys (SWG)**, one of the top 5 accelerators according to European top tier VCs (as ranked by Sifted in December 2022) that focuses on entrepreneurs in underserved markets and fast tracks their growth, and
- **Business Angels Europe (BAE)**, mobilising the investment potential of national angel investment communities from East to West of Europe, bringing access to investment from the most experienced European angel groups to back growth-potential entrepreneurs from start up to scale up.

Figure 3. Comprehensive 6-Month Startup Acceleration Journey.

The EmpoWomen Accelerator programme consists of two 3-month phases:

Accelerator Phase 1: Months 1-3: Building and Growing Your DeepTech Business

Delivered by StartUp Wise Guys (SWG), enables the selected cohort of women entrepreneurs to experience an intensive programme, focused on addressing key growth challenges in building their business and tailored to their personal goals. Support will be delivered through a programme of online webinar sessions, delivered by experts in business, industry and deep technologies. This will be accompanied by access to one on one expert mentoring sessions offered throughout the programme.

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Annex 1. Guidelines for Applicants

Through a series of weekly modules, participants will work through key business growth areas including:

1. Your core Business Purpose and Values
 - Refining your mission, vision, and culture
 - Identifying the key steps for growth journey
 - Establishing your own personal goals and KPIs
2. Product Execution and Sales
 - Establishing your Product Market fit
 - Ensuring an effective commercialisation and sales strategy
3. Technology Product development and effective planning
 - Ensuring the deep tech product or service is unique and innovative and addresses the needs of your customers and market customers.
 - How to build a defensible competitive position in the market and protecting your IP
4. Focus and Execution:
 - How to stay on top of the game and push your business to the next level
 - How to be resilient and address the next crisis.
5. Sales and Team Basics
 - Sales, marketing, and branding; Sales funnel: who and how to reach out
 - Building your team and skill set
 - Developing your leadership skills
6. Developing your Funding Strategy and understanding your options
 - Preparing your business to engage with investors
 - Identifying your investment needs and options

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Annex 1. Guidelines for Applicants

- Understanding the basic legal and commercial aspects of fundraising

One on One Mentoring: Each participant will also have direct access to monthly individual mentoring sessions throughout the 6-month Accelerator programme. This will be provided by individual experts who will be matched to the entrepreneurs and tailored to the technology and sector focus and will enable the women entrepreneurs to focus on their own business goals and identified challenges and needs.

Progress Review Day

At the end of Phase 1 of the Accelerator programme, there will be a Progress Review Day, where women entrepreneurs will have an in-depth review of their progress in achieving their business objectives (KPIs). This will be carried out by SWG, together with BAE and provide valuable feedback and key insights for the next phase of the Acceleration programme.

Phase 2: Months 4-6: Ensuring your Deep Tech Business is Ready for Investment

This second phase of the Accelerator programme enables the cohort of women entrepreneurs to gain an in-depth understanding of the whole investment process, addressing any challenges and barriers for women entrepreneurs when seeking investment and looking at the specific requirements for attracting investment for a deep tech business and relevant to their specific sector or market, combined with direct engagement with investors.

This will be provided by Business Angels Europe, delivered by experienced Angel and early stage investors in deep tech and relevant industry sectors. This phase of the programme also offers opportunities for direct engagement with experienced investors in deep tech and the BAE Club of Leading Angel Investment groups across Europe, including potential to showcase at relevant investor events. The three-month programme, delivered in weekly online webinar sessions will cover the following:

1. Developing your Funding Strategy and Creating an attractive Deep Tech Investment proposal.

These sessions will be designed to enable women deep tech entrepreneurs to understand the critical aspects of creating their funding strategy, identify when and why they need funding, the different sources available, and how to strategize their approach to secure investment.

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- Understanding the Investment Market and equity supply chain -what finance is right for your business
- What are Business Angels, angel syndicates and their added value
- Identifying your funding strategy from Angel to Scale-up
- How to use Convertible Loans and ASAs and SAFE
- What Investors are looking for in a deep tech business and how to develop an attractive investment proposal to address the needs of investors.
- Your Toolkit to Attract Investors

2. Making a Winning Pitch, effective Negotiations and the Due Diligence process

These sessions will be aimed at mastering the art of pitching and understanding the intricacies of business valuation, due diligence and negotiation with investors

- Mastering the art of pitching and understanding what investors look for
- How to effectively engage with investors after the pitch
- Preparing for Due Diligence ; scope and purpose and how to respond to investors needs
- Understanding how to value your business – art or science?
- How to negotiate and understand what investors require.

3. Closing the Deal, Navigating the legal process; Getting the most from your investors post deal

These sessions are designed to take the entrepreneurs through the challenges of finalizing the deal, understanding the legal processes and documents and ensuring that they are well positioned to make the most of their investors post deal.

- Understanding the key elements of the Term Sheet and finalising the deal
- Legal processes – understanding the core documents
- Understanding the Cap table Closing the deal
- What can go wrong and when to walk away
- Making the most of your investors post investment and gaining added value

Annex 1. Guidelines for Applicants

Demo Day

The conclusion of the Accelerator Programme will be marked by a Presential Demo Day at which the cohort of women entrepreneurs will each present their business to an audience of invited investors with deep tech expertise and experience from across relevant industries and sectors. The Pitch presentations offer the opportunity of attracting investor interest and gaining direct feedback, one on one interactions with investors and establishing the potential for further follow up meetings. Attendance at the Presential Demo Day is mandatory for all beneficiary startups.

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7. Beneficiaries' Responsibilities

The selected organisations are indirectly beneficiaries of European Commission funding. As such, they are responsible for the proper use of the funding and ensure that the recipients comply with obligations under Horizon specific requirements. The obligations that are applicable to the recipients include:

7.1 Conflict of interest

Beneficiaries must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the sub-project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests'). They must formally notify to the EmpoWomen coordinator without delay any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interest and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation. The EmpoWomen coordinator may verify that the measures taken are appropriate and may require additional measures to be taken by a specified deadline. If the sub-contracted consortium member breaches any of its obligations, the sub-contract may be automatically terminated. Moreover, costs may be rejected.

7.2 Data protection and confidentiality

During implementation of the sub-project and for four years after the end of the sub-project, the parties must keep confidential any data, documents or other material (in any form) that is identified as confidential at sub-contract signing time ('confidential information').

7.3 Promotion of the action and EU Funding visibility

The beneficiary must promote their participation in the EmpoWomen project and the benefits obtained as a result of participating in the programme. They will provide targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner and to highlight the financial support of the EC. The EmpoWomen Communication Team will guide, provide materials and support these communication activities. Unless the European Commission or the EmpoWomen coordinator requests, or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.), any publicity, including at a conference or seminar or any type of information or promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, presentation etc.), and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

Annex 1. Guidelines for Applicants

- display the EU emblem;
- display the EmpoWomen logo.

When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. This obligation to use the European emblem in respect of projects to which the EC contributes implies no right of exclusive use. It is subject to general third-party use restrictions which do not permit the appropriation of the emblem, or of any similar trademark or logo, whether by registration or by any other means. Under these conditions, the Beneficiary is exempted from the obligation to obtain prior permission from the EC to use the emblem. Further detailed information on the EU emblem can be found on the [Europa web page](#). Any publicity made by the beneficiary in respect of the project, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, must specify that it reflects only the author's views and that the EC or EmpoWomen project is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The EC and the EmpoWomen consortium shall be authorized to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- the name of the beneficiary;
- contact address of the beneficiary;
- the general purpose of the project;
- the amount of the financial contribution foreseen for the project; after the final payment, and the amount of the financial contribution actually received;
- the geographic location of the activities carried out;
- the list of dissemination activities relating to the foreground;
- the details/references and the abstracts of scientific publications relating to the foreground and, if funded within the sub-project, the published version or the final manuscript accepted for publication;
- the publishable reports submitted to the EmpoWomen consortium;
- any picture or any audio-visual or web material provided to the EC and EmpoWomen in the framework of the project.

The beneficiary shall ensure that all necessary authorisations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the EC and EmpoWomen does not infringe any rights of third parties. Upon a duly substantiated request by the beneficiary, EmpoWomen, if such permission is provided by the EC, may agree to forego such publicity if disclosure of the information indicated above would risk compromising the beneficiary's security, academic or commercial interests.

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7.4 Financial audits and control

The European Commission (EC) will monitor compliance with the financial support conditions outlined in Annex 1 of the EmpoWomen Grant Agreement by beneficiaries and third parties. The EC may conduct financial audits, which may be conducted by external auditors or by EC services, including the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF). Beneficiaries must make all detailed information and data available to the EC or any authorized representative for audit purposes. The beneficiary must keep all sub-project deliverables and documents for up to five years from the end of the project.

7.5 Internal communication

Each of the teams selected to join the programme must nominate a primary contact point that will act as a coordinator during the duration of the programme.

- Provide any notice in writing to the EmpoWomen programme coordinator.
- Notify immediately of any change of persons or contact details to hello@empowomen.eu. The address list shall be accessible to all concerned.

7.6 External communication and open data

Each funded organisation will be publicly listed at EmpoWomen public channels like social networks or website. The funding disbursed by the EmpoWomen consortium to each of the beneficiaries will be made public under a dataset that will be uploaded into an open a free repository as it is Zenodo.

Annex 2

Application Form

OPENING: 8th of January 2024

CLOSING: 8th of March 2024 at 17:00 CET

Project Website: www.empowomen.eu

Open Call platform: https://bit.ly/EmpoWomen_OC1

All the Open Call documents and templates are available for download at www.empowomen.eu

V1.0 26/12/2023

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Table of Contents

1. Legal and contact INFO	3
1.1 Participant Information (contact point)	3
1.2 Organisation information	3
1.3 Eligibility self-declaration	3
2. Project description	5
2.1 Technology behind your startup.....	5
3. Excellence	7
4. Impact	8
5. Implementation	10
6. Areas of Interest for Acceleration Programme	11
7. Privacy policy	12
8. Declaration of Honour	13

1. Legal and contact INFO

1.1 Participant Information (contact point)

- Lead applicant () *:
 - Name
 - Surname
 - Country
 - Email
 - Phone number:
 - Gender (male/female/other/prefer not to say)
- Position within the company*:

1.2 Organisation information

- - Organization legal name*:
 - Organization short name*:
 - Legal address*:
 - City/Town*:
 - Province/Region*:
 - Country*:
 - Phone number*:
 - Organization Website *:
 - VAT number*:
 - PIC number *:

1.3 Eligibility self-declaration

1. Was your startup founded or co-founded by women? *: **YES/NO**

Annex 2. Application Form

- 1.1 Additionally, does the founder or co-founder currently hold key management positions (such as CEO, CTO, or equivalent roles) within the company at the time of submission? *: **YES/NO**
2. Is your startup currently a legally registered entity? *: **YES/NO**
3. Does your company have less than 6 years since registration as of the submission deadline date? *: **YES/NO**
 - 3.1 Please specify the date of registration
4. Does your company meet the criteria to be classified as a Small and Medium-sized Enterprise (SME) according to the European Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC? *: **YES/NO**
5. The company can be considered a 'deep tech' company*: **YES/NO**
6. Has your company raised less than 1M€ in equity or public funding until the submission date? *: **YES/NO**
7. Can you confirm that your proposal is unique and has not been previously funded in the Women TechEU initiative or any other initiative to avoid double funding? *: **YES/NO**

2. Project description

2.1 Technology behind your startup

- 1- **Provide a summary of your startup, outlining its core activities, the problems it addresses, and the products or services it currently offers in the market. (max 500 characters) *: This description will be made public if you are selected.**
- 2- Which of the deep tech technologies is your company addressing? **(multiple choice) ***:
 - Advanced Computing /Quantum Computing
 - Advanced Manufacturing
 - Advanced Materials
 - Aerospace, Automotive and Remote Sensing
 - Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, including Big Data
 - Biotechnology and Life Sciences
 - Communications and Networks, including 5G
 - Cybersecurity and Data Protection
 - Electronics and Photonics
 - Internet of Things, W3C, Semantic Web
 - Robotics
 - Semiconductors (microchips)
 - Sustainable Energy and Clean Technologies
 - Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, Metaverse
 - Web 3.0, including Blockchain, Distributed Ledgers, NFTs

Applicants are advised that, in a subsequent phase following the evaluation process, if selected, they will be asked to complete an Ethics Self-Assessment. This step is crucial to ensure ethical compliance in the areas of research and development. Full cooperation is expected from the chosen startup in this regard.

- 3- How close is the solution to market readiness? Please select the right TRL ([technology readiness level](#))? *:
 - TRL9
 - TRL8
 - TRL7
 - TRL6

Annex 2. Application Form

- TRL5
- TRL4 or lower

4- Does your company own any IP under which the tech is rooted? *:

- Fully owned, or exclusive license acquired
- Shared with someone else or non-exclusive license obtained
- Access to the IPR is being negotiated and the deal will close in 12 months' time
- Access to the IPR is still unclear
- No IPR discovered or protection planned
- Other (please specify)

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3. Excellence

- 1- How does your project address the specific objectives set forth in the EmpoWomen call? **(max 500 characters) ***:
- 2- Can you provide specific examples of the technological innovation your project brings? **(max 500 characters) ***:
- 3- How has your project surpassed conventional standards in specific aspects, and what sets its technological approach apart from existing solutions? **(max 500 characters) ***:
- 4- What notable achievements have you reached so far, and how do they demonstrate the viability and progress of the project? **(max 500 characters) ***:
- 5- Highlight any collaboration or partnership that enhances the excellence of your project. **(max 500 characters) ***:
- 6- What are the specific support needs from EmpoWomen, the activities to be carried out, and the coaching and mentoring needed for the advancement of women in technology in your project? **(max 500 characters) ***:
- 7- What is the startup's ambition and commitment to scale up? **(max 500 characters) ***:
- 8- Offer a Forecast for Your Business Over the Next 4 Years (2024-2026) *:
 - a. Table including Sales, Number of Employees, Private Funding, and Grants

4. Impact

- 1- Please upload a Business Model Canvas (**template link**)***PDF**:
- 2- Business Overview and Plans, Including Marketing Activities (**max 500 characters**) *:
- 3- Clearly outline your target market: if you plan to create new markets or disrupt existing ones in Europe or worldwide, incorporating details on size, growth rate, trends, as well as considerations for market barriers, time to market, and potential customers. (**max 1000 characters**) *:
- 4- Identify Both Direct and Indirect Competitors in the Market (**max 500 characters**) *:
- 5- Share Your Fundraising Plans (Select One) *:
 - a. The company has already secured funding from investors or business angels and is seeking follow-up funding rounds.
 - b. The company is currently in advanced negotiations with potential investors or business angels.
 - c. The company has obtained public grant(s) and is seeking funding from investors or business angels next.
 - d. The company has not secured funding but has a clear plan to acquire public grants.
 - e. The company has not yet secured any funding, except for modest investments from the founders.
 - f. Other (please specify) (**max 200 characters**)
- 6- Specify Your Sources of Funding (Select Multiple) *:
 - a. Friends and family
 - b. Angel investor
 - d. Debt
 - e. Venture Capital
 - f. Public funding
 - g. Own funding
 - h. Other (please specify) (**max 100 characters**)
- 7- Provide Historical Business Information (2021-2023) *:
 - a. Table including Sales, Private Funding, and Grants
- 8- Explain the economic, social, and environmental impacts of your solution (**max 500 characters**) *:

Annex 2. Application Form

9- Are you looking for substantial funding but the risks involved are too high for private investors alone to invest the full amount needed? **(max 500 characters) ***:

10- Please Upload Your Pitch Deck. **(*PDF) ***:

Intellectual Property Aspects (IPR):

11- What measures have you taken to protect the intellectual property of your solution or innovation? **(max 500 characters) ***:

12- How do you plan to maintain and enforce your intellectual property rights as your project progresses? **(max 500 characters) ***:

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5. Implementation

- 1- Key Team Member (up to 3) *:
 - Name: [Full Name] *:
 - Surname: [Surname] *:
 - Email: [Email] *:
 - CV*: in PDF
 - LinkedIn: [LinkedIn Profile]
 - Brief Experience: [Brief description of relevant experience] **(max 500 characters)** *:
- 2- Number of team members: **[Number]** *:
- 3- How do you ensure gender-equitable representation in leadership roles and key decisions within your startup? **(max 500 characters)** *:
- 4- What measures have you implemented to ensure equal opportunities for professional development for women in your team? **(max 500 characters)** *:
- 5- How do you assess and address potential gender barriers that may arise in the workplace? **(max 500 characters)** *:
- 6- What is your team's experience in the advanced technology industry (deep tech), and could you highlight a significant achievement of the founders or team members in this field? **(max 500 characters)** *:
- 7- Is there previous startup experience in the team? If yes, was it successful? **(max 500 characters)** *:
- 8- Will the female founder or co-founder actively participate in the acceleration program, dedicating at least 75% of her time to the process? **(yes / no)** *:

6. Areas of Interest for Acceleration Programme

In order to tailor our Acceleration Program to best meet your startup's needs, please provide insights into the specific areas where you believe your venture would benefit the most. Your responses will help us align our resources and expertise to support your growth effectively.

Product Development and Innovation:

- Current product development status and goals
- Innovative features or technologies in your product

Sales and Market Expansion:

- Current sales strategies and market presence
- Expansion plans and target demographics

Pitching and Communication:

- Pitching capabilities and strategies
- Notable achievements or challenges in communicating your value proposition

Legal and Compliance Considerations:

- Approach to legal aspects, including compliance and intellectual property
- Specific legal challenges your startup has encountered

Fundraising Strategies:

- Current fundraising efforts and experiences
- Funding goals and strategies

Additional Areas of Interest:

Specify any other specific areas or challenges requiring special attention in the acceleration program. Please elaborate.

7. Privacy policy

By submitting this form, you agree and confirm the following:

- We have read, understood, and will comply with the open call details and requirements stated in the Guidelines for applicants.
- All information provided in the EmpoWomen application submitted by our entity is correct and complete.
- Our company is not in any situation which would exclude us from receiving financial support from third parties.
- Our company is not under liquidation or in financial difficulty.
- Our company is not subject to any conflict of interest in connection with the EmpoWomen open call consortium or evaluators.
- We will inform the EmpoWomen consortium, without delay, of any situation considered a conflict of interest or which could raise a conflict of interest.
- We will process any personal data in compliance with the applicable EU and national law on data protection.

8. Declaration of Honour

By submitting this form I, the applicant:

hereby certify that (subject to the additional declarations below):

1. The information provided for this project is correct and complete.
2. The information concerning the legal status in the Application for my organisation is correct and complete and concurs with the stipulations outlined in the Guidelines for Applicants, including its annexes (if applicable).
3. My organisation commits to comply with the eligibility criteria set out in the call for proposals for the entire duration of the action.
4. My organisation:
 - is committed to participate in the action;
 - has stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain the activity throughout the action and to provide any counterpart funding necessary;
 - has or will have the necessary resources needed to implement the action;
5. My organisation:
 - is NOT subject to an administrative sanction (i.e., exclusion or financial penalty decision).
6. My organization is NOT in one of the following exclusion situations :
 - bankrupt, being wound up, having the affairs administered by the courts, entered into an arrangement with creditors, suspended business activities or subject to any other similar proceedings or procedures;
 - in breach of social security or tax obligations.
7. My organisation (or persons having powers of representation, decision-making or control, beneficial owners or persons who are essential for the award/implementation of the grant): are NOT in one of the following exclusion situations :
 - guilty of grave professional misconduct ;
 - committed fraud, corruption, links to a criminal organisation, money laundering, terrorism-related crimes (including terrorism financing), child labour or human trafficking;
 - shown significant deficiencies in complying with main obligations under an EU procurement contract, grant agreement or grant decision;
 - guilty of irregularities within the meaning of Article 1(2) of Regulation No 2988/95;

Annex 2. Application Form

- created under a different jurisdiction with the intent to circumvent fiscal, social, or other legal obligations in the country of origin (including creation of another entity with this purpose).
8. My organisation is NOT subject to a conflict of interest in connection with this grant and will notify — without delay — any situation which could give rise to a conflict of interests.
 9. My organisation has NOT and will NOT, neither directly nor indirectly, grant, seek, obtain, or accept any advantage in connection with this grant that would constitute an illegal practice or involve corruption.
 10. My organisation has not received any other EU grant for this project and will give notice of any future EU grants related to this project AND of any EU operating grant(s) given to my organisation.
 11. My organisation is aware that false declarations may lead to rejection, suspension, termination or reduction of the grant and to administrative sanctions (i.e., financial penalties and/or exclusion from all future EU procurement contracts, grants, prizes and expert contracts).

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Annex 3

Leaflet

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Apply to the EmpoWomen Open Call #1 from 8 January to 8 March 2024

Our Objective: To create an exclusive support programme for female founders and entrepreneurs leading deep tech startups from widening areas to grow into tomorrow's female tech leaders and put women at the forefront of deep tech in Europe.

What we offer?

- Up to 45,000€ in equity-free funding
- Six-month Acceleration programme including Vouchers to Business Angels Investment Readiness
- Access to Top-Level Mentors Vouchers
- Attendance to Tech-events Vouchers
- Awards for Top Startups per Cohort (up to 15,000€)

How to apply

Step 01

Review the open call documentation provided on the website

Step 02

Complete the application form

Step 03

Ensure that your application is submitted by 17:00 CET on March 8, 2024

Do you have more questions?

www.empowomen.eu
helpdesk@empowomen.eu

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Annex 4

EmpoWomen Open Call #1 Announcement

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Announcement of an open call for recipients of financial support

Action acronym: EmpoWomen

Action grant agreement number: 101120693

Action full name: Acceleration programme empowering women-led deep tech startups in Widening Areas

The action EmpoWomen, funded by the European Union, provides financial support to third parties as a means to achieve its own objectives.

EmpoWomen_OC#1 is committed to providing equity-free funding to empower up to 11 startups led by women. In its dedication to advancing women-led startups in deep tech, EmpoWomen provides essential financial support divided into two key components:

- **Grant:** The grant is the primary funding received by startups, with a maximum limit of 45,000 EUR. This sum aims to support various vital activities for the development of emerging businesses. The grant will be disbursed in three distinct phases, carefully integrated into EmpoWomen's acceleration program. Each phase represents a significant milestone in the progress of startups and is designed to strategically support their growth.
- **Demo Day Prizes:** During Demo Day, startups have the opportunity to stand out and be recognized through specific prizes. These prizes are distributed as follows:
 - Prize 1: 15,000 EUR
 - Prize 2: 11,500 EUR
 - Prize 3: 6,000 EUR

In addition to providing equity-free funding for startups, they will also be part of a 6-month acceleration programme of dedicated intensive support to the selected group of women deep tech entrepreneurs, with a view to enabling them to significantly boost their business growth and increase their potential to access investment. The acceleration programme incorporates three distinct vouchers aimed at enhancing the entrepreneurial journey.

- **Voucher 1.** Access to Events: Covering expenses for attending EU tech summits. Participation in at least 2 events per startup. The events (different from the Demo Day) will be communicated by the EmpoWomen consortium during the execution of the acceleration program. Valued at 5,000 EUR per startup.
- **Voucher 2.** Business Angels (BA) Investment Readiness Programme: Dedicated programme on business angels' investment provided directly by real angel investors who have an overlap within their expertise/geography. Valued at 2,400 EUR per startup.
- **Voucher 3.** Mentoring: up to 16 sessions of a dedicated mentor for the company. Valued at 5,000 EUR per startup.

Deadline: 08/03/2024, 17:00 CET

Expected duration of participation: 6 months (all phases).

Maximum amount of financial support for each third party: up to 60,000€.

Call identifier: EmpoWomen_OC#1

Language in which application should be submitted: English

Web address for further information: www.empowomen.eu

Guidelines for applicants: <https://empowomen.eu/wp-content/themes/expowomen/assets/files/guide-for-applicants.pdf>

Email address for further information: hello@empowomen.eu

Helpdesk: helpdesk@empowomen.eu